

An Empirical Study of Privacy-Utility Trade-offs in Gaze-Based Authentication for Extended Reality

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Abstract

Extended Reality (XR) systems that enable gaze-based authentication raise significant privacy concerns due to the sensitive nature of gaze data. While prior work has demonstrated the feasibility of gaze as a behavioral biometric, little is known about how privacy-preserving mechanisms affect verification performance in realistic XR settings. This paper empirically investigates the privacy-utility trade-off of gaze-based verification in XR. We first establish a non-private baseline by evaluating gaze features and classification models under a verification protocol. We then apply differential privacy to aggregated gaze features and analyze how varying privacy budgets impact authentication performance. Results show a gradual degradation rather than a sharp collapse, revealing practical operating regions where meaningful privacy protection can be achieved without prohibitive loss in verification accuracy. Our findings provide empirical guidance for the design of privacy-aware gaze-based authentication systems in XR environments.

CCS Concepts

• **Human-centered computing** → **Mixed / augmented reality; Empirical studies in HCI**; • **Security and privacy** → **Usability in security and privacy; Authentication**; • **Computing methodologies** → **Machine learning approaches**.

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1 Introduction

Extended Reality (XR) technologies are rapidly moving from experimental systems to everyday platforms for communication, entertainment, education, and professional work. As XR head-mounted displays (HMDs) mediate access to personal data, accounts, and services, reliable user authentication is a critical requirement for secure and trustworthy immersive experiences. Research on XR authentication has primarily focused on improving security and resistance

to attacks; however, even when effective, such approaches often prioritize performance gains and user experience while giving limited attention to the privacy implications of capturing and processing highly sensitive behavioral data. For example, gaze data used in biometric authentication encode not only identity-related cues but also rich information about cognition, attention, and mental state, raising concerns about misuse, re-identification, and long-term profiling.

In this work, we treat gaze-based biometrics as a concrete and representative use case to study an underexplored problem: how to protect the privacy of gaze data while maintaining practically viable verification performance in XR. As eye tracking has become a standard capability of HMDs, understanding this trade-off is important for the responsible deployment of gaze-based authentication mechanisms. While differential privacy has been explored primarily for gaze analytics tasks, authentication presents distinct challenges because it relies on biometric verification protocols and identity-related signals that must remain discriminative even under privacy-preserving transformations. We therefore examine gaze-based authentication in a verification setting and empirically analyze how privacy-preserving transformations influence authentication outcomes. First, we establish a non-private performance baseline by evaluating gaze features and classification models. We, then, introduce differential privacy to perturb gaze data and investigate how varying privacy budgets affect verification accuracy.

Our main contributions are two-fold: (i) we demonstrate the feasibility of gaze-based verification in XR using a lightweight authentication task and (ii) we empirically characterize the privacy-utility trade-off using differential privacy and identify practical privacy budget ranges showing that meaningful privacy protection can be achieved without prohibitive loss in authentication performance.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 discusses related work and research objective; Section 3 presents the methodology of our study; Section 4 presents the results; Section 5 discusses implications and limitations of our work and proposes directions for future research.

2 Related work and research objective

2.1 Related work

2.1.1 User authentication in XR. Research categorizes authentication in XR according to the factor it relies on: knowledge-based, possession-based, and inherence-based, with their effectiveness varying depending on contextual and risk considerations [Katsini

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et al. 2026]. Knowledge-based authentication is the most widely explored approach due to its familiarity and low deployment cost. Typical examples include PIN entry [Abdelrahman et al. 2022; Zhang et al. 2017], graphical passwords [Düzgün et al. 2022], and gesture-based secrets [Islam et al. 2018; Ragozin et al. 2022]. However, XR introduces challenges related to input precision, cognitive load, and vulnerability to observation and shoulder-surfing attacks, often requiring mitigation through randomized layouts [Mathis et al. 2021] and dynamic visual cues [Winkler et al. 2015]. Possession-based authentication has received little attention in XR, with approaches relying on external devices such as one-time passwords and QR codes scanned via HMDs [Chan et al. 2015; Latvala et al. 2018]. Inherence-based authentication leverages biometric characteristics and offers a promising alternative. Physiological biometrics (e.g., iris and pupil features) provide strong distinctiveness but are constrained by environmental and hardware factors [Boutros et al. 2020; Yan et al. 2020], while behavioral biometrics (e.g., gaze patterns) support implicit and continuous authentication at the cost of greater variability [Lohr and Komogortsev 2022; Shen et al. 2019].

2.1.2 Biometrics in XR authentication. Biometrics in XR leverage intrinsic user characteristics to reduce memorization burden, enable seamless interaction, and align with HMDs' sensing capabilities. At the same time, continuous capture and processing of biometric data raises concerns around privacy, misuse, and long-term identifiability. Physiological biometrics rely on relatively stable physical traits (e.g., iris texture, pupil response, facial features), with prior work exploring iris recognition using cameras [Boutros et al. 2020; Li and Huang 2017], pupil light reflex under visual and auditory stimulation [Yan et al. 2020; Zhu et al. 2023], and facial and head-related signals [Li et al. 2024, 2023; Wang et al. 2023] in XR. While these approaches offer strong discriminative capacity, their robustness can be affected by illumination, sensor quality, and user comfort. In contrast, behavioral biometrics capture user interaction patterns in XR through gaze, head movement, gait, gestures, and task performance [Lohr and Komogortsev 2022; Shen et al. 2019]. While they support continuous and implicit authentication, making them attractive for XR, they are inherently variable and, when collected in raw form, may reveal sensitive information beyond identity.

2.1.3 Gaze-based authentication. Gaze has been employed in three main ways for authentication: explicit gaze-based secrets, implicit gaze-based authentication, and gaze-supported multi-factor authentication [Katsini et al. 2020]. Here, we focus on implicit gaze-based authentication, which verifies identity from largely unconscious eye-movement patterns without requiring users to remember a secret. These approaches follow the biometric pipeline of enrolment (capturing a template) and recognition (matching new samples to stored templates), relying on gaze exhibiting sufficient uniqueness and temporal stability. Most systems represent gaze using aggregated features derived from eye-tracking metrics such as fixation and saccade statistics, scanpath descriptors, and higher-level measures (e.g., gaze entropy and fixation density maps) [Li et al. 2018; Lyamin and Cherepovskaya 2015]. In XR, recent work shows that gaze can form distinctive behavioral signatures suitable for unobtrusive authentication during natural interaction [Liebers et al. 2021; Lohr and Komogortsev 2022; Lohr et al. 2024]. However, performance varies with context (stimulus, task, device), temporal effects,

and population size, particularly when moving from identification (1:N) to verification (1:1) settings [Sluganovic et al. 2018]. Although gaze biometrics are increasingly adopted due to their availability on HMDs, they encode rich cognitive and perceptual information, making privacy protection a key open challenge [Agarwal et al. 2024; Katsini et al. 2020].

2.1.4 Privacy-preserving methods for gaze data. Because gaze data can reveal sensitive information, privacy must be protected across the full processing pipeline, including capture, transmission, storage, and inference. Existing approaches can broadly be grouped into (i) data minimization and decentralization, (ii) representation obfuscation, and (iii) cryptographic secure computation. A first line of work reduces exposure by keeping raw eye-tracking data local, for example through federated learning, enabling gaze models to be trained without centralizing raw streams and aligning well with XR deployments where on-device inference and periodic model updates can be integrated into HMD runtimes [Rehman et al. 2026]; other works further combine federated learning with secure multi-party computation to support collaborative gaze estimation training without exposing raw eye-image data [Elfares et al. 2024]. Another line of work obfuscates gaze inputs or features through transformations such as noise injection, blurring, or synthesis of privacy-enhanced gaze data; for example, *PrivateGaze* learns user-side transformations producing obfuscated images compatible with black-box gaze estimation models [Du et al. 2024], while *PrivacEye* detects privacy-sensitive situations using gaze behavior and egocentric scene images and automatically disables the scene camera via a mechanical shutter [Steil et al. 2019b]. Cryptographic techniques further enable privacy-preserving gaze processing. Homomorphic encryption, for example, allows secure scanpath comparison without revealing raw data, enabling privacy-preserving verification when authentication relies on sequence similarity [Özdel et al. 2024]. Another research direction protects gaze datasets before public release by applying privacy mechanisms such as k-anonymity and plausible deniability to synthesize gaze samples and reduce user re-identification while preserving statistical properties and task utility [David-John et al. 2022, 2023]. At the feature level, perturbation and downsampling reduce re-identification risk, while differential privacy (DP) provides a principled mechanism for injecting calibrated noise to bound information leakage [Krishna Prakasha and Sumalatha 2025; Özdel et al. 2024]. Recent work applies DP to gaze data to reduce inference of sensitive attributes and user identity, while studies also show that gaze behavior can reveal perceived privacy sensitivity, enabling adaptive privacy-preserving mechanisms [David-John et al. 2023; Elfares et al. 2025; Steil et al. 2019a].

2.2 Research objective and questions

Building on prior work on gaze-based authentication and emerging privacy-preserving techniques, this paper investigates how to design gaze-based authentication in XR to achieve reliable user verification while limiting exposure of sensitive gaze data. While existing research demonstrates the feasibility of gaze as a behavioral biometric, little is known about how privacy-enhancing mechanisms, particularly DP, affect verification performance in biometric authentication scenarios in XR. To address this gap, we formulate two complementary research questions.

RQ₁ To what extent can gaze behavior elicited by an authentication task support reliable user verification, and which classification model is most suitable under a standard, non-private setting?

This question establishes a performance-oriented baseline by validating the authentication task and identifying an effective verification model; the resulting configuration serves as a fixed reference point for subsequent privacy analysis.

RQ₂ How does applying DP to gaze data affect verification performance, and within which range of privacy budgets can meaningful privacy guarantees be achieved without unacceptable loss in accuracy? This question constitutes the main contribution of the paper, empirically characterizing the privacy-utility trade-off of gaze-based authentication in XR; by varying the privacy budget, we identify a practical operating region where gaze data can be meaningfully protected while maintaining usable verification performance.

3 Methodology

3.1 RQ1. Baseline authentication and model suitability

3.1.1 Authentication task. We used a passive image-viewing task to elicit structured yet naturalistic eye-movement behavior suitable for gaze-based authentication in XR. During each authentication attempt, we presented participants with a static preview image displayed centrally in the XR environment. We instructed them to observe the image freely. We used the same image stimulus across all participants and sessions to ensure consistency of visual input. Each viewing period lasted approximately 10-15 seconds and required no memorization, decision-making, or explicit interaction, minimizing cognitive load while eliciting repeatable, individual-specific gaze patterns. We considered only gaze data recorded during image presentation, treating each viewing instance as a single authentication attempt.

3.1.2 Verification protocol. We formulated gaze-based authentication as a binary *verification* task. In this setting, a user claims an identity, and the system must decide whether to accept or reject the authentication attempt based solely on gaze behavior recorded during the authentication task. Because the dataset contains only legitimate authentication attempts, impostor trials were generated synthetically following standard practice in biometric verification. Specifically, for each genuine attempt, we constructed impostor trials by pairing the gaze features from an authentication session with a claimed identity from a different participant. This procedure preserves the statistical properties of real gaze data while enabling controlled evaluation of false acceptance behavior. The number of impostor trials was balanced with the number of genuine trials to ensure stable estimation of verification performance metrics. Model training and evaluation were performed using stratified k -fold cross-validation, ensuring that genuine and impostor trials were consistently represented across folds and that no authentication session appeared simultaneously in both training and testing sets.

3.1.3 Participants. We analyzed gaze data collected from $N = 42$ participants (29 self-identified men and 13 self-identified women), aging between 19 and 51 years ($M = 35$, $SD = 11$). Each participant

performed between three and six authentication sessions; each session was treated as an independent sample in our analysis.

3.1.4 Apparatus. All data were collected using an *HTC Vive XR Elite* headset equipped with an inward-facing eye-tracking system. The eye tracker captured binocular gaze data at approximately 120 Hz, with an accuracy of around $\pm 0.5^\circ - 1.0^\circ$ depending on calibration quality and viewing conditions. The headset provided stereoscopic displays with a resolution of 1920×1920 pixels per eye, a refresh rate of 90 Hz, and a field of view of approximately 110° .

3.1.5 Gaze features and metrics. The gaze features and metrics were organized into six behavioral categories: (i) *temporal* metrics (*mean_dwell_time*, *std_dwell_time*), (ii) *fixation-based* metrics (*fixation_count*, *mean_fixation_duration*), (iii) *saccade-based* metrics (*mean_saccade_amplitude*, *mean_saccade_velocity*), (iv) *spatial* metrics (*scanpath_length*, *gaze_efficiency*), (v) *entropy-based* metrics (*aoi_entropy_bits*, *transition_entropy_bits*, *revisit_rate*), and (vi) *general* metrics (*num_unique_AOIs*). We selected these features as they summarize gaze behavior at the session level and do not retain the original temporal ordering of the raw gaze trajectory, instead representing gaze behavior through aggregated statistical summaries suitable for biometric verification.

3.1.6 Model selection. We evaluated twelve classification models with differing inductive biases: (i) *Logistic Regression* and *Linear Support Vector Machines (SVM)* as linear baselines, (ii) *Radial Basis Function (RBF)* and *Polynomial SVMs* to capture non-linear decision boundaries, (iii) *Decision Trees*, *Random Forests*, *Extra Trees*, *Gradient Boosting*, and *XGBoost* as tree-based models capturing feature interactions, (iv) *k-Nearest Neighbors* as an instance-based method, (v) *Gaussian Naive Bayes* as a probabilistic baseline, and (vi) a *Multilayer Perceptron (MLP)* as a neural model. All models were trained using identical feature representations and preprocessing pipelines.

3.1.7 Evaluation metrics. We assessed verification performance using common biometric evaluation metrics: (i) the area under the Receiver Operating Characteristic curve (ROC-AUC) as a threshold-independent measure of class separability and (ii) the Equal Error Rate (EER) as the operating point at which false acceptance and false rejection rates are equal, providing a concise summary of the security-usability trade-off. Higher ROC-AUC values and lower EER values indicate stronger authentication performance.

3.1.8 Procedure. We followed a four-step approach: (i) we issued an open call for participation through announcements and online mailing lists, directing interested individuals to a dedicated study webpage where they could review detailed study information and select a convenient timeslot, and upon registration participants provided informed consent prior to participation and were free to withdraw at any time without penalty, participation was voluntary and no monetary compensation was provided, and the study was conducted in accordance with internal ethical review procedures at the authors' institution. (ii) upon arrival at the study venue, a researcher provided an overview of the procedure, answered questions, and addressed potential concerns, after which participants wore the HMD and completed an eye-tracker calibration and familiarization task; (iii) during the authentication task, participants

Figure 1: Applying DP to gaze and facial data extracted during XR authentication (adapted from [Raptis et al. 2024])

performed multiple attempts, with each attempt constituting a single authentication session, while the HMD continuously recorded gaze data throughout task execution; and (iv) after completing all sessions, gaze data were processed and analyzed in three stages: (a) extraction of session-level gaze features from each authentication attempt, (b) evaluation of classification models under a verification protocol to identify a suitable baseline for gaze-based authentication (RQ_1), and (c) subsequent use of the selected model to examine the privacy-utility trade-off under differential privacy constraints (RQ_2).

3.2 RQ_2 . Privacy-utility trade-off

3.2.1 Threat model. We consider a scenario where gaze feature representations used for authentication may be stored or transmitted outside the XR device, potentially exposing sensitive behavioral information. An adversary with access to this data could attempt to infer identity or secondary attributes from gaze patterns. To mitigate such risks, we apply DP at the feature level before model training and evaluation, corresponding to a local privacy setting where sensitive gaze information is perturbed prior to potential release.

3.2.2 Privacy-preserving gaze representation. To investigate the privacy-utility trade-off, we introduce controlled noise to the gaze feature representation using a DP mechanism. Specifically, we apply additive Laplace noise to each gaze feature, simulating the release of privacy-preserving gaze data. Noise magnitude is governed by a privacy budget parameter ϵ , where lower values correspond to stronger privacy guarantees and higher perturbation, while larger values approach the non-private setting. Following the standard definition of DP, neighboring datasets are defined as gaze feature vectors differing in a single authentication session. Since all features were normalized to the range $[0, 1]$, the global sensitivity of each feature dimension is bounded by $\Delta f = 1$, and Laplace noise is sampled from $\text{Lap}(0, \Delta f/\epsilon)$. Figure 1 illustrates an example of applying DP to iris data. Noise is applied independently to each feature dimension after feature normalization, and no noise is added to identity labels. This corresponds to a feature-level local DP setting in which gaze representations are perturbed prior to model training or potential data release.

Table 1: Verification performance for RQ_1 across evaluated models (mean \pm std).

Model	ROC-AUC	EER
Polynomial SVM	0.73 ± 0.02	0.34 ± 0.02
RBF-SVM	0.74 ± 0.03	0.33 ± 0.03
Linear SVM	0.65 ± 0.03	0.39 ± 0.03
Gaussian NB	0.37 ± 0.04	0.59 ± 0.03
Logistic Regression	0.34 ± 0.01	0.63 ± 0.02
kNN	0.23 ± 0.04	0.74 ± 0.03
Decision Tree	0.07 ± 0.02	0.88 ± 0.02
Gradient Boosting	0.06 ± 0.02	0.88 ± 0.02
XGBoost	0.05 ± 0.01	0.88 ± 0.02
Extra Trees	0.04 ± 0.01	0.88 ± 0.02
Random Forest	0.04 ± 0.01	0.88 ± 0.02
MLP	0.15 ± 0.03	0.78 ± 0.04

3.2.3 Privacy budget configuration. We evaluate authentication performance under multiple privacy budgets to capture a range of privacy levels, from weak to strong protection. We consider $\epsilon \in \{\infty, 100, 50, 25, 10, 5, 2, 1, 0.5, 0.25, 0.1, 0.05\}$, where $\epsilon = \infty$ denotes the conceptual non-private baseline corresponding to the original, non-perturbed gaze features. Through this configuration, we systematically analyze how increasing privacy constraints affect verification performance and identify operating regions where acceptable authentication accuracy can be maintained.

3.2.4 Evaluation protocol under DP. Based on the results of RQ_1 , we set the selected classifier as the authentication backbone for all RQ_2 experiments. For each privacy budget ϵ , we repeat the verification protocol described in RQ_1 using the noise-perturbed gaze features. Model training and evaluation follow identical cross-validation splits and preprocessing pipelines to ensure comparability across privacy levels. Verification performance is assessed using ROC-AUC and EER, allowing direct comparison between privacy-preserving and non-private configurations. All reported results are aggregated across folds and summarized using mean and standard deviation.

4 Results

4.1 RQ_1 . Baseline authentication and model suitability

Table 1 summarizes verification performance across all evaluated models. Overall, kernel-based methods achieved the best authentication performance, with the Polynomial SVM and RBF-SVM yielding the highest ROC-AUC values (≈ 0.73 and ≈ 0.74 , respectively) and the lowest Equal Error Rates (EERs) (≈ 0.33). These results indicate that gaze-based authentication cues exhibit a non-linear structure that is not well captured by linear decision boundaries alone. Linear models (Logistic Regression and Linear SVM) performed moderately, suggesting limited linear separability in the gaze-feature space. In contrast, tree-based ensemble methods (Random Forests, Extra Trees, Gradient Boosting, and XGBoost) performed close to chance level, with high EER values, indicating poor suitability for score-based verification under the examined protocol. The resulting ROC-AUC values below 0.5 indicate that the predicted scores are

effectively inverted relative to the positive class, reflecting inverted score ordering rather than meaningful predictive performance. Similarly, instance-based (k NN), probabilistic (Gaussian Naive Bayes), and neural (MLP) models underperformed, likely due to the limited number of authentication sessions per participant. Based on these findings, we select the RBF-SVM as the baseline model for the subsequent experiment, as it provides strong and stable verification performance.

4.2 RQ2. Privacy-utility trade-off

Figure 2 illustrates the privacy-utility trade-off for gaze-based authentication under increasing DP constraints. As the privacy budget ϵ decreases, authentication performance degrades gradually rather than suddenly, revealing a smooth transition from usable verification to near chance-level discrimination. In the non-private setting ($\epsilon = \infty$), verification performance plateaus, serving as the reference point for subsequent comparisons within the privacy-evaluation protocol. Note that this value corresponds to the performance of the selected baseline classifier within the privacy-evaluation protocol used for the DP experiments, which applies the same feature-processing pipeline and aggregates results across repeated cross-validation runs. As a result, the $\epsilon = \infty$ point represents the non-private configuration within this privacy-evaluation protocol, and may therefore differ slightly from the model-selection results reported in Table 1. For moderate privacy budgets ($\epsilon \approx 0.5 - 5$), ROC-AUC increases steadily while remaining close to the non-private baseline, with overlapping error bars, indicating that meaningful privacy protection can be achieved without significant loss in authentication performance. Stronger privacy constraints ($\epsilon \leq 0.1$) lead to a more evident decline toward chance-level performance, reflecting increased obfuscation of identity-related gaze signals. Overall, the observed trend highlights a practical operating region where privacy and usability can be jointly balanced, rather than a sharp performance collapse; specifically, privacy budgets in the range $\epsilon \approx 0.5 - 5$ maintain verification accuracy close to the non-private baseline while keeping performance degradation within the observed variance.

5 Discussion

5.1 Findings and implications

A first finding of our work is that gaze-based features can support reliable user verification in XR environments through a lightweight, unobtrusive authentication task. Among the evaluated models, kernel-based classifiers achieved the strongest verification performance, indicating that identity-related gaze patterns exhibit a non-linear structure. Another finding is that introducing differential privacy at the feature level led to a gradual degradation in authentication performance rather than a sharp collapse, showing how privacy-preserving perturbations influence biometric verification performance in XR. Therefore, our results reveal a practical operating region of privacy budgets in which meaningful privacy protection can be achieved while maintaining usable verification accuracy.

These findings introduce several theoretical and practical implications. Regarding theoretical implications, our work reframes gaze not only as an interaction signal but also as a sensitive behavioral

Figure 2: Privacy-utility trade-off for gaze-based authentication under DP. ROC-AUC is reported as mean \pm standard deviation across cross-validation folds and repetitions for different budgets ϵ (log scale). Lower ϵ values correspond to stronger privacy guarantees.

biometric whose utility and privacy risks can be jointly modeled. By demonstrating that authentication performance degrades gradually under differential privacy constraints, the findings provide empirical evidence that privacy preservation and biometric verification utility can be jointly balanced, and position privacy as a tunable design dimension.

Regarding practical implications, the findings show that privacy-preserving gaze-based authentication is feasible under realistic XR conditions, offering actionable guidance for system designers through identifiable operating ranges of privacy budgets. For practitioners and industry stakeholders, this supports the responsible deployment of gaze-based authentication mechanisms that align with privacy-by-design principles without compromising usability. The work also provides an empirical framework for evaluating privacy-utility trade-offs in gaze-based verification, and highlights how implicit sensing and authentication can be integrated into XR interaction pipelines in a privacy-aware manner while maintaining compliance with data protection regulations (e.g., GDPR).

5.2 Limitations and future work

While the study provides empirical insights into the privacy-utility trade-off of gaze-based authentication in XR, we should acknowledge several limitations: (i) the participant sample size is moderate and may limit generalizability to larger and more diverse user populations, (ii) authentication performance was evaluated using a single, controlled visual stimulus, which may not capture variability across tasks and interaction contexts, (iii) impostor attempts were synthetically generated rather than collected from real adversarial scenarios, and (iv) privacy protection was applied at the feature level using a single DP mechanism, without considering alternative threat models. Building on these limitations, future research should (i) evaluate gaze-based authentication under more diverse XR tasks,

stimuli, and interaction conditions, (ii) examine longitudinal stability and robustness against real-world adversarial behavior, (iii) explore complementary privacy-preserving approaches, such as local differential privacy, on-device learning, and hybrid cryptographic methods, to further strengthen privacy guarantees in XR authentication systems, and (iv) examine how privacy-preserving gaze-based authentication integrates into broader XR system contexts, including its robustness under adversarial conditions such as impersonation and replay attempts.

6 Conclusion

This paper examined gaze-based authentication in XR through the lens of privacy preservation, focusing on the trade-off between verification performance and protection of gaze data. We established a non-private baseline using a lightweight authentication task and identified a suitable baseline model for gaze-based verification. Building on this baseline, we applied differential privacy to gaze features and analyzed how varying privacy budgets affect authentication outcomes. Our results show a gradual performance degradation rather than a sharp collapse, revealing a practical operating region where meaningful privacy guarantees can be achieved while maintaining usable verification performance.

Privacy and ethics statement

Gaze data may reveal sensitive behavioral information and pose privacy risks; this work evaluates differential privacy mechanisms that limit information leakage while preserving authentication performance. All data were collected with informed consent, anonymized before analysis, and processed under ethical approval via internal ethics review at Human Opsis (Approval No. 65X716).

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